

ARCHITECTURE OF ANCIENT KHOREZM AND CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS

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Khorezm – is considered as ancient heart of world civilization. It is famous with its rare architectural monuments. Architectural constructions built in the cities are one of the scales showing the development of statehood. In this article, we mention monuments of ancient cities of Khorezm and its analysis of architectural relics related to their construction [1].

The word “VARA” in Avesto is related with the word “PIL” which is meant construction of city, walls, fortresses, fortification. For instance, in II-III centuries A.D. Turpok kala, and in IV–X centuries Kat (Fil) were capital of Khorezm. An old part of Gurganj kala determined on V – IV centuries B.C [2]. Tuprok kala pertaining to I – III centuries, an ancient monument that was capital of Khorezm. The fortress is surrounded by a wall that is 8 m in thickness. The palace is built on 14m-higher foundation comprising raw brick and sand. There are 100 rooms and 40x40m-sized 3 towers in the castle. Each tower is 25 m high (imag.1).

Image.1

Kalaliqir kala – in rectangular shape, had an area of 1000x700 m. The walls are strengthened with towers. It had four gates. The defense walls of the fortress are built on

sand. 40x40x10cm-sized bricks laid on the top of the foundation of packed mud that is 1.15–1.30-m in height [4]

Oqchaxon kala – according to its plan it is rectangular and it is divided in 2 parts – upper & lower fortresses. There was high barricade wall in the distance of 4 m from defense walls of the fortress. Kat kala – situated in Beruniy city, the fortress is built with raw bricks and in nowadays its walls is weathered. The defense walls had 2 layers and its outside is strengthened with rounded towers. In western-southern corner of the fortress has 54x54-sized rectangular pavilion. Its walls are done with packed mud and thickness of lower part is 6 m & the height is 10 m. The design of architectural monuments of ancient Khorezm is being used until now, especially packed mud walls are obvious evidence of it. Till recent days, architectural constructions were mostly studied by archaeologists, accepted as archeological item and were used to identify its archeological ages.

Now we are studying this issue in the point of view of constructing technology. Our aim is to study method & building techniques of architectural monuments, materials that are used for them in ancient Khorezm. It is known that ancient Khorezm has its own trend in school of architecture. Mud was main constructing material since ancient times in Khorezm. Mainly mud was used as connecting material with raw bricks, plaster, and packed mud in the process of construction. At the end of VII and in VI centuries B.C., raw brick & packed mud made of mud is used in constructing buildings in ancient Khorezm.

In constructions of ancient Khorezm, packed mud mainly used as foundation, raw bricks are used building upper parts of walls. In the construction of Kozaliqir fortress rectangular big 52x26x60 sized bricks used, as well as since V-IV centuries B.C. rectangular 40x40x10 bricks were used. Changing rectangular bricks into quadrangle was an innovation in architecture.

Big ancient raw bricks were laid in the sun in pressed mold. Broken crushed straw, bits gravel, sand and this kind of closely packing tightly materials were added in order to make quality bricks. Raw bricks not only used in building walls, but also used in covering inside of rooms end roofs. In ancient Khorezm ripen bricks were also used together with raw bricks. Ripen bricks were used in construction of Tuprok kala as a first time. Marbles, sandstones were used in building together with packed mud end bricks.

Alabaster end carved decorations were widely used in Khorezm architecture. 40x40x5m sized bricks of carved alabaster were found in Kalaliqir – I. Decoration of guestroom of Tuprok kala with engraved carved indicates how this craft were ancient it was.

Other constructing materials such as wood were also important in statehood architecture. The building made of willow was easy and endurance to soft earthquake that take place here. We can show Ko'zaliqir as a very ancient example of using woods in architecture of Khorezm.

Cross beam and doors made of wood widely used in Khorezm as well.

The method of building on tall artificial platform, rammer made of raw bricks and sand or mud was widely used in enormous big buildings in Khorezm. Very simple of platform were used in the walls of Tuprak kala end Kalaliqir – I.

In order to build defense walls the top of 15-m in width foundation were made cell and was filled with sand-gravel. After that building process started. As of researcher thinking, using as platform in building fortress in sand has important technical aspects. First of all, sand protects from subsoil waters. Secondary, rammed platform with sand could support building because freely and entirely shaking in earthquake. As well as it does not allow to crack & divide. In Khorezm, outside walls were designed with pilyastr and pilon.

Pilyastr and pilon served as support in strengthening walls of fortress. This kind of pilyastr used in the wall of Tuprok kaka as well. Connecting with girder among the walls of big and small building were the most problems all times. In architecture of fortresses in ancient Khorezm – there were method of laying roof made of bricks wood in the shape of dome. Method of laying roof with woods is the most ancient in statehood history.

At the end of VII and VI centuries B.C. in Kozaliqir – I, Oqsoch this kind of laying straight roofs appeared. Laying straight roof with woods method is being continued since ancient time until now. As well as, since IV centuries B.C. methods of covering roof the shape of dome or jupiter-tree. Trapezoid –shape bricks made in special mold is used and only building dome.

Dome end cupola type laying roof is strongly developed in architecture of ancient Khorezm. Top of 4.5m in wide room in Koykirilgan kala is laid with dome-shape (imag.2.).

Image.2

Above mentioned methods of architecture of ancient Khorezm was great success of architect of Central Asia. And these methods arrive up to us.

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